

Rice varieties and resistance genes tested for brown planthopper response in China.

Variety	Gene
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>
IR26	<i>Bph 1</i>
IR42	<i>bph 2</i>
ASD7	<i>bph 2</i>
H105	<i>bph 2</i>
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>
Babawee	<i>bph 4</i>
PTB 21	2 unidentified
PTB 33	2 unidentified
Sinna Sivappu	2 unidentified
Sudu Hondarawala	2 unidentified
TN1	none

10 provinces — Kwangtung, Kwansi, Fukien, Chekiang, Hupeh, Hunan, Kweichow, Szechuan, Anhwei, and Kiangsi (see figure). They infested TN1 seriously but were light on Mudgo, IR26, ASD7, Rathu Heenati, Babawee, PTB 21, PTB 33, Sudu Hondarawala, and Sinna Sivappu.

Survival of BPH nymphs on TN1 was significantly greater than on varieties with resistance genes. TN1 supported a larger population and allowed greater development of BPH.

The area of honeydew stained by ninhydrin on TN1 was greater than the area

Distribution of brown planthopper biotypes in China.

on resistant varieties. The heaviest honeydew was excreted by BPH fed on TN1. ■

The results indicate that BPH collected from the different regions of China are biotype 1. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Inheritance of tolerance for aluminum toxicity in Brazilian rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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Four Brazilian upland rice cultivars — Pratão, IAC 25, Perola, and Bico Ganga — and their F₁ and F₂ progenies from a diallel cross were evaluated for response to 0, 30, and 60 ppm Al in nutrient solutions. The characters studied were plant height, root length, and shoot and root dry weight of 25-day-old seedlings after 21 days of growth in the solutions.

Pratão and IAC 25 were more tolerant of aluminum toxicity than Pérola

and Bico Ganga. At 0 ppm Al, Pratão had shorter stems (2%), shorter roots (10%), and less dry weight (49%) than Pérola, but at 60 ppm Al had longer stems (23%), longer roots (15%), and greater dry weight (195%).

Tolerance for aluminum toxicity was controlled by more than one pair of genes, with transgressive segregation and quantitative inheritance observed. Specific combining ability was more important than general combining ability, indicating a greater nonadditive genetic factor. Specific combining ability for all the characters studied at different aluminum concentrations was least in the Pérola-IAC combination. Genotypic correlations were greater than phenotypic correlations, indicating that genetic components had greater contribution than environmental components. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Sensitivity of some modern rice varieties to high temperature at anthesis in the western districts of Orissa, India

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Anthesis or blooming is the only growth stage at which rice plants are sensitive to high temperatures. Spikelet sterility is mainly attributed to pollen desiccation. Jennings and others found some varieties, such as Hoveyze from south Iran, fertile at temperatures higher than 45° C when others are sterile.

Preliminary observations on the effect of maximum day temperature during